

VALIDATION OF IN SILICO-DESIGNED GAPDH PRIMERS FOR qPCR-BASED REFERENCE GENE ANALYSIS IN NORMAL BLOOD CELLS AND LEUKEMIA CELL LINES

Abdurakhimova Jamilakhon Bakhtiyor kizi

Second-year Master's student

National University of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Jaloliddin Mirjalilovich

PhD., Institute of Plant Substances Chemistry

Alimuhamedova Orzugul Bahrievna

Institute of Plant Substances Chemistry

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ABSTRACT

The reliability of RT-qPCR-based gene expression analysis critically depends on the selection of stable reference genes, among which GAPDH is one of the most widely used. In this study, we validated in silico-designed GAPDH primer pairs for their application as an internal control in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) and leukemia cell lines (CCRF-CEM and Jurkat). The constructed primer system demonstrated high specificity and amplification efficiency, with primer pair 5 showing optimal performance based on key design and amplification parameters. These results confirm the suitability of the selected GAPDH primers for accurate normalization in gene expression studies involving both normal and malignant blood cells.

Reverse transcription quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR) is a widely used method for quantitative gene expression analysis, requiring stable reference genes for accurate normalization [1]. Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) is one of the most commonly used housekeeping genes due to its constitutive expression [2]. The amplification analysis demonstrated specific and efficient detection of GAPDH across peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) and leukemia cell lines (CCRF-CEM and Jurkat), with clearly defined exponential phases (*Fig.1*).

Figure 1.

Jurkat cells showed the earliest amplification ($Ct \approx 16$), followed by CCRF-CEM ($Ct \approx 17$), while PBMC samples demonstrated later amplification ($Ct \approx 23$). Among the eight designed primer pairs, primer pair 5 showed optimal performance and was selected as the most suitable candidate (F: 5'-CGGATTTGGTCGTATTGGG-3'; R: 5'-GTTGAGGTCAATGAAGGGT-3'). No amplification was observed in the negative control, confirming assay specificity. Overall, the selected primer pair is suitable for RT-qPCR-based normalization in both PBMCs and leukemia cell lines.

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